

Study of furan derivatives formation from the carbohydrate raw material under thermal conditions using PY-MS and FTIR spectroscopy methods

Cherepanov I.S.¹, Egorova A.I.¹, Tarasova D.A.¹

¹Udmurt State University, Izhevsk, Russia, cherchem@mail.ru

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The results of furan structural fragment's formation in *D*-maltose (as model carbohydrate system) thermodestruction products study are presented. Using derivative IR Fourier transform spectroscopy and pyrolysis-mass spectrometry (PY-MS) methods It has been shown that in processes of alkaline cleavage and dry caramelization of the initial carbohydrate the polymeric structures, containing furan heterocycles of varying substitution degree, form as a result of intramolecular condensations.

Formation of furan derivatives from carbohydrate may be presented as scheme Figure 1, **A**, illustrating intramolecular activation by the attack of O(C₂)-atom on the anomeric C₁-centre [1]. Cleavage of glycoside bond provides the monosaccharides and furfural (peaks at *m/z* = 68, 82, 96 in PY-MS spectra), further condensations lead to polymeric products, which structure depends on reaction conditions and our earlier investigation assume formation of α - and β -furan humic-like systems [2].

Figure 1. **A**, Proposed furfural formation mechanism; **B**, second derivative FTIR-spectra of solid phases: 1. – maltose alkaline cleavage products; 2. – maltose dry thermodestruction products; 3. – alkaline cleavage products after dry thermodestruction.

Analysis of 3150-3100 cm⁻¹ FTIR spectral area of solid phases of various maltose thermodestruction products allows to estimate furan cycles substitution degree [2]. Second derivative FTIR spectra (Figure 1, **B**) show difference between α/β -[C-H] content in various polymeric furans: alkaline cleavage products (intensive doublet at 3109 and 3122 cm⁻¹ in spectrum 1) contain significant part of non-substituted rings (free =C-H bonds), as soon as dry thermodestruction solid phases of initial disaccharide and its alkaline cleavage products (spectra 2 and 3) are more condensed (no sharp signals). It is also postulated, that the [=C _{α} -H]-fragments react by the electrophilic substitution mechanism, but the [=C _{β} -H]-centers transform via oxidative condensation pathway. These experimental facts are in agreement with the literature data obtained [1] and may be used in biotechnologies, perspective as a synthetic platform for biomass transformation to heterocyclic compounds.

References

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